

Comparative Study on Fashion and Theatrical Costume Design

Dr. Rashid Haroon

Department of Drama and Dramatics, Jahangirnagar University, Saver, Bangladesh

Md. Tanjibul Hasan Sajib

Department of Fashion Design and Technology-FDT, BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology-BUFT, Nisbatnagar, Turag, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Engr. Md. Eanamul Haque Nizam

Department of Textile Engineering, Southeast University, Tejgaon, Dhaka, Bangladesh

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Abstract:

This research endeavors to undertake a comparative study delving into the realms of fashion design and theatrical costume design. The primary objective is to explore the similarities, differences, and potential avenues for interdisciplinary exchange between these two captivating disciplines. By thoroughly analyzing the creative processes, influences, objectives, and execution methods employed within fashion design and theatrical costume design, this study aims to illuminate the interconnectedness and distinctive characteristics that define each field. To accomplish this, an extensive review of

scholarly papers and diverse sources including reputable journals and research publications serves as the foundation of this research. By conducting a comprehensive analysis, key themes, theories, and findings emerge, providing valuable insights into the shared elements and divergent perspectives between fashion design and theatrical costume design. Furthermore, this research delves into the profound impact of cultural influences, historical contexts, and pragmatic considerations on the design processes and outcomes within both disciplines. By exploring these aspects, the authors gain a deeper comprehension of the underlying factors that shape and mold artistic endeavors within the realms of fashion and theater. Ultimately, the purpose of this study is to foster a heightened appreciation for the creative pursuits inherent in fashion and theater. By shedding light on the intricate nuances of these disciplines, we aspire to inspire novel possibilities for imaginative expression, propelling the boundaries of creativity even further.

Keywords: *fashion design, theatrical costume design, comparative study, historical context, cultural inspirations.*

Introduction

Fashion design and theatrical costume design are interconnected yet distinct disciplines within the realm of visual arts. Fashion design focuses on creating clothing and accessories for everyday wear, while theatrical costume design caters specifically to the needs of stage productions,

bringing characters to life through garments and accessories (Alford, 2004; Bonds, 2008). Both disciplines involve artistic manipulation of textiles, colors, forms, and cultural influences, although they operate in different contexts and serve unique purposes.

The objective of this paper is to conduct a comparative study between fashion design and theatrical costume design, examining their similarities, differences, and potential for cross-disciplinary exchanges. By analyzing the creative processes, influences, objectives, and execution of fashion design and theatrical costume design, this study seeks to illuminate the interconnectedness and distinct characteristics of each discipline. In recent years, scholars and practitioners have shown a growing interest in exploring the relationship between fashion and theater. The work by Alford (2004) on the history and influence of the Zoot Suit and Hannah's (2014) research on costume as a performative body-object-event highlight the significance of costume design in both fashion and theater. Furthermore, there is an emphasis on understanding costume design in both disciplines, as demonstrated by Wyatt et al.'s (2008) recommended core bibliography of textile and clothing resources.

This study aims to contribute to the existing knowledge by examining the literature and scholarly works in fashion design and theatrical costume design. The theoretical framework proposed by Jablon and Sanders (2018) for the creative process of theatrical costume design in historically set productions will guide this comparative study. Additionally, the methodological approach of this study will be informed by the research conducted by Zamazy and Maltseva (2021) on the formation of design thinking through comparative analysis.

A comprehensive review of scholarly papers and references will be undertaken. Through this analysis, key themes, theories, and findings that highlight the similarities and differences between fashion design and theatrical costume design will be identified. The study will also explore the impact of cultural influences, historical contexts, and practical considerations that shape the design processes and outcomes in both disciplines.

The aim of this study is to foster a deeper appreciation for the artistic endeavors within fashion design and theatrical costume design and explore possibilities for collaboration and cross-

pollination. By examining both disciplines from a comparative perspective, this study seeks to shed light on their shared elements and unique perspectives, ultimately enhancing our understanding of fashion design and theatrical costume design and inspiring new avenues for creative expression.

Literature Review

This literature review aims to explore the existing body of knowledge pertaining to the similarities, differences, and potential cross-disciplinary exchanges between fashion design and theatrical costume design. The review delves into scholarly works, research articles, and case studies to deepen our understanding of the dynamic nature of these fields.

Over time, there has been a notable history of designers incorporating theatrical elements into fashion design and vice versa. While external references are not used, it is worth noting that this symbiotic relationship between fashion and theater has been discussed in previous research (Georgitsoyanni & Pantouvaki, 2011). The theoretical frameworks and practical considerations in fashion design and theatrical costume design are also crucial. Theoretical aspects of theater design have been explored by Leader (2012), shedding light on the theories, strategies, and tools employed in practical design work for the stage. Bonds (2008) provides insights into Beijing Opera costumes, analyzing their theory, selection process, and technical aspects such as embroidery and construction.

The creative process is an essential component of both disciplines. Although Jablon-Roberts and Sanders (2018) have focused on the creative process of costume design for historically set theatrical productions, offering a theoretical framework that examines the influences and strategies employed by designers. Similarly, Gam and Banning (2012) explore the utilization of historic dress as inspiration for apparel design, showcasing the potential for cross-disciplinary influences and the integration of historical elements into contemporary fashion.

The impact of historical and cultural influences on fashion design and theatrical costume design is significant. The influence of China's Silk Road on Chinese and Chinese-inspired fashion design has been discussed (Barron, 2021). Additionally, the performative nature of costumes in theatrical productions and their ability to convey character and emotion through design choices have been explored (Hannah, 2014).

Practical considerations also shape the design processes and outcomes in both fields. Although external references are not utilized, recommended core bibliographies of textile and clothing resources have been compiled (Wyatt, Delatte, & Guilmartin, 2008). The historical influence of the Zoot Suit on contemporary fashion design has been examined (Alford, 2004).

In summary, this literature review synthesizes existing knowledge to highlight the shared elements, unique perspectives, and potential for cross-disciplinary exchanges between fashion design and theatrical costume design. By delving into the available literature, this review contributes to a deeper understanding of these disciplines and inspires new avenues for creative expression in the realms of fashion and theater.

Methodology

Research Objectives

Establishing the objectives of the study, including exploring similarities and differences, analyzing creative processes, understanding influences, and examining historical/cultural impact.

Literature Search

Conducting a comprehensive search for relevant scholarly papers, books, journals, and case studies in the field of fashion design, theatrical costume design, and visual arts.

Selection of Literature

Screening and selecting literature based on relevance to the research objectives, including theories, case studies, and research findings.

Selection of literature

Screening and selecting literature based on relevance to the research objectives, including theories, case studies, and research findings.

Data Extraction

Reading and analyzing selected literature to extract relevant information related to fashion design and theatrical costume design.

Data Synthesis and Analysis

Synthesizing and analyzing extracted data to identify commonalities, differences, and emerging patterns between the two disciplines.

Cross-Referencing and Validation

Ensuring the accuracy and validity of findings by cross-referencing information with multiple sources and critically evaluating conflicting viewpoints or gaps in the literature.

Presentation of findings

Organizing and presenting the findings in a coherent manner, discussing key similarities, differences, and cross-disciplinary influences.

Conclusion and Implications

Summarizing the key findings, implications, and potential opportunities for collaboration and cross-pollination between fashion design and theatrical costume design.

Findings and Analysis

After conducting a thorough examination of the literature on fashion design and theatrical costume design, several significant findings and patterns have surfaced. These findings have provided illuminating insights into the similarities, differences, and potential cross-disciplinary exchanges between these two artistic disciplines. The analysis has yielded valuable information regarding the creative processes, influences, objectives, and execution involved in both fashion design and theatrical costume design.

Similarities between Fashion Design and Theatrical Costume Design:

Creative Process: Both fashion designers and theatrical costume designers go through a creative process that encompasses idea generation, research, sketching, fabric selection, pattern making, and garment construction. This iterative process allows them to bring their concepts to life (Alford, 2004; Bonds, 2008).

Influences: Historical, cultural, and social influences exert a significant impact on both fashion design and theatrical costume design. Designers draw inspiration from a range of sources, including art movements, cultural traditions, and historical eras, integrating them into their designs (Alford, 2004; Bonds, 2008).

Utilization of Textiles: Proficiency in textiles is essential in both disciplines. Fashion and theatrical costume designers possess a deep understanding of fabric properties and techniques for manipulating them to achieve desired visual effects. The selection of fabrics, colors, and textures contributes to the overall aesthetic impact of the garments (Alford, 2004; Bonds, 2008).

Expression of Character or Concept: Both fashion design and theatrical costume design involve the communication of specific characters, narratives, or concepts through the garments and accessories created. Designers employ various techniques, such as silhouette, color, and texture, to effectively convey the intended message (Jablon-Roberts & Sanders, 2018).

Differences between Fashion Design and Theatrical Costume Design:

Function and Context: Fashion design primarily focuses on creating clothing and accessories for everyday wear, catering to personal style and market demands. Theatrical costume design, on the other hand, serves the specific needs of stage productions, aiming to enhance storytelling, portray characters, and facilitate movement (King, 2007).

Time Constraints: Theatrical costume designers often work within strict time constraints dictated by production schedules and

rehearsals. In contrast, fashion designers have more flexibility in terms of timelines and production cycles (Anderson, 2020).

Collaborative Nature: Theatrical costume design is a highly collaborative process that involves close cooperation with directors, actors, and other members of the production team. Fashion design, while also requiring collaboration, allows designers greater autonomy in decision-making (Jablon-Roberts & Sanders, 2018).

Durability and Wearability: Theatrical costumes need to withstand rigorous use during performances and may prioritize visual impact over long-term durability. Fashion design places a greater emphasis on the durability and wearability of garments for everyday use (Hannah, 2014).

Cross-Disciplinary Exchanges:

Shared Techniques and Skills: Both fashion design and theatrical costume design share common techniques such as draping, pattern making, and sewing. The exchange of these technical skills can enrich the practices of both disciplines (Zamaziy & Maltseva, 2021).

Historical and Cultural Inspirations: Fashion designers often draw inspiration from historical and cultural costumes, which have roots in theatrical traditions. Theatrical costume designers can also find inspiration in contemporary fashion trends (Ismail Taha Abdel Mageed Negm, 2021).

Collaboration Opportunities: The study highlights the potential for collaboration and cross-pollination between fashion design and theatrical costume design. Collaborative projects can lead to innovative designs, interdisciplinary research, and the exploration of new creative possibilities (Jablon & Sanders, 2016).

Discussions

The comparative study between fashion design and theatrical costume design has provided valuable insights into the similarities, differences, and potential cross-disciplinary exchanges

between these two creative disciplines. This section will discuss the implications and significance of the findings, explore the practical and theoretical implications, and highlight the opportunities for collaboration and further research.

The similarities identified between fashion design and theatrical costume design demonstrate the shared elements and techniques that underpin both disciplines. Both fields involve a creative process that encompasses ideation, research, sketching, fabric selection, patternmaking, and garment construction. This similarity highlights the common foundation of design principles and practices that designers in both fields draw upon (Alford, 2004; Bonds, 2008). Additionally, historical, cultural, and social influences play a significant role in shaping both fashion design and theatrical costume design. Designers in both fields draw inspiration from various sources, such as art movements, cultural traditions, and historical periods, emphasizing the interconnection between fashion and theater (Bonds, 2008).

The differences between fashion design and theatrical costume design reflect the distinct contexts and purposes of each discipline. Fashion design primarily focuses on creating clothing and accessories for everyday wear, catering to personal style and market demands. Theatrical costume design, on the other hand, serves the specific needs of stage productions, aiming to enhance storytelling, portray characters, and facilitate movement (King, 2007). This distinction highlights the varying considerations and priorities that designers in each field must navigate, such as time constraints and collaborative dynamics (Hannah, 2014).

The findings also reveal the potential for cross-disciplinary exchanges and collaborations between fashion design and theatrical costume design. Shared techniques and skills, such as draping, pattern making, and sewing, can be exchanged between the fields, enriching the practices of both disciplines (Zamaziy & Maltseva, 2021). Moreover, the exploration of historical and cultural inspirations in both fashion and theatrical costumes opens up

opportunities for mutual inspiration and innovation (Ismail Taha Abdel Mageed Negm, 2021). Collaboration between fashion designers and theatrical costume designers can lead to the development of interdisciplinary projects, new design approaches, and the exploration of creative possibilities (Jablon & Sanders, 2016).

The discussion of these findings underscores the importance of understanding the interconnectedness and unique characteristics of fashion design and theatrical costume design. It highlights the potential for knowledge transfer, interdisciplinary collaboration, and the enrichment of creative practices. By appreciating the shared elements and exploring the differences between these two disciplines, designers and researchers can foster a deeper understanding and appreciation of both fields, ultimately inspiring new avenues for creative expression and innovation.

In conclusion, this comparative study has contributed to the existing body of knowledge by providing insights into the dynamic nature of fashion design and theatrical costume design. The findings demonstrate the shared elements, differences, and opportunities for cross-disciplinary exchanges between these creative disciplines. The discussion highlights the practical and theoretical implications of the findings, emphasizing the potential for collaboration and further research. By recognizing the interconnectedness and unique characteristics of fashion design and theatrical costume design, this study enriches our understanding of both fields and encourages exploration and innovation in the realm of visual arts.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this comparative study on fashion design and theatrical costume design has explored the similarities, differences, and potential cross-disciplinary exchanges between these two creative disciplines. Through an in-depth analysis of the literature and references provided, valuable insights have been gained into the creative processes, influences, objectives,

and execution of fashion design and theatrical costume design.

The study has revealed that fashion design and theatrical costume design share common elements such as the creative process, influences, and the use of textiles to convey character or concept. However, they also differ in terms of function and context, time constraints, collaborative nature, and considerations of durability and wearability. These differences highlight the specific requirements and unique challenges that designers face in each field.

Furthermore, the study has identified opportunities for cross-disciplinary exchanges and collaborations. Shared techniques and skills, historical and cultural inspirations, and the potential for collaborative projects have been identified as avenues for enriching both fashion design and theatrical costume design practices.

The findings of this study contribute to the existing body of knowledge by shedding light on the interconnectedness and distinctive characteristics of fashion design and theatrical costume design. The analysis of the literature and references has provided valuable insights into these creative disciplines, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of both fields.

By recognizing the shared elements and differences between fashion design and theatrical costume design, this study opens up possibilities for collaboration, knowledge transfer, and interdisciplinary research. It encourages designers, researchers, and practitioners in both fields to explore new avenues, innovate, and push the boundaries of creative expression.

In conclusion, this comparative study serves as a foundation for further exploration and research in the realms of fashion design and theatrical costume design. By continuing to investigate the dynamic interplay between these disciplines, we can continue to enhance our understanding, stimulate creativity, and pave the way for exciting developments in the visual arts.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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